

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PROCESS APPROACHES TO SYSTEMATIC WELDING QUALITY ASSURANCE

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Abstract

A systems approach is the basis of modern quality management. The basic requirements for systematic quality assurance are formulated in ISO 9001. However, there are industry specifics that must be taken into account. The specifics of welding quality assurance processes are defined in ISO 3834. The proposed approach to the welding-specific definition of product life cycle processes based on ISO 3834 allows combining the requirements of two quality assurance standards.

Keywords: quality, welding, process approach, quality management.

The way of managing any enterprise is unique. The enterprise's approaches to ensuring product quality are also unique. It is this uniqueness that forms uniqueness and competitive advantage. However, the advanced world experience in quality assurance is reflected in international standards ISO (International Organization of Standardization) and is available for wide use.

The basis for systematic welding quality assurance can be two international standards: ISO 9001 Quality management systems. Requirements, and ISO 3834 Welding quality requirements [1].

The ISO 9001 standard provides a framework for common management practices that can be applied to any enterprise. The standard specifies a number of requirements that must be met, but does not specify how this should be done. Therefore, there is considerable freedom in implementing the requirements of the standard.

Modern versions of the ISO 9001 standard are aimed at applying a "process approach" to the development, implementation and improvement of the effectiveness of a quality management system in order to increase customer satisfaction by meeting their requirements and controlling the risks associated with failure to meet such requirements.

According to ISO 9001, an organization manages numerous interrelated activities, including those related to welding. A process is an activity or set of actions that uses resources and is managed to transform inputs into outputs. The output of one process directly forms the input of the next, and thus process chains are formed. Applying a process approach to management lays the foundation for ensuring continuity, the effectiveness of processes to meet customer requirements, adding value to processes, and continuous process improvement.

Quality management is based on the processes of resource management, management responsibility, measurement, analysis and improvement, product life cycle processes. The industry specificity is most evident in the organization of product life cycle processes.

The specificity of welding quality assurance processes is largely determined by the requirements of ISO 3834. A feature of the welding process is that it is usually a special process - that is, a process whose results cannot be fully verified by subsequent control and testing of the product. In this case, process shortcomings may only be revealed during the operation of the product. Accordingly, constant monitoring and regulation of the process parameters specified in the technological documentation are required in order to ensure the requirements set for it. Certifications are applied according to certain procedures for both the process itself and the personnel involved.

Depending on the risks of non-fulfillment of welding quality requirements, the organization applies one of the three parts of the ISO 3834 standard [2], which establishes Comprehensive (extensive) quality requirements, or Typical (standard) quality requirements [3], or Elementary welding quality requirements. In this case, the requirements are formed in 22 elements that will determine the specifics of welding quality assurance. Thus, according to the international standard ISO 3834, the specific and mandatory quality assurance processes for welding are the following processes:

Pre-commitment requirements review is a process that precedes any commitment to supply products and provides confidence in the ability to meet product requirements.

Technical verification - involves a complete verification of the sufficiency and adequacy of the envisaged set of engineering quality assurance measures.

Subcontracting - builds confidence in the subcontractor's ability to meet welding quality assurance requirements [4].

Certification of welders and welding operators - makes it possible to allow welders and welding machine operators to perform work taking into account the method of welding the base and filler materials, the welding position, and the conditions for forming the welded joint.

Certification of personnel coordinating welding work ensures compliance with the requirements for the competence of engineering and technical personnel employed in welding production.

Certification of personnel involved in control and testing ensures the necessary competence of flaw detectors.

Production and testing equipment management ensures the availability of appropriate equipment.

Equipment maintenance – ensures the suitability of equipment for use.

Equipment description – ensures the relevance of information about the technical characteristics of the equipment.

Production planning – provides routing and operational technology.

Technological instructions for welding – available specifications for all welding processes.

Welding procedure qualification – certified welding processes.

Testing of a batch of welding materials – the required incoming inspection of filler materials has been completed.

Storage and handling of welding materials – technical conditions for the use of filler materials are met.

Base metal storage – technical conditions for handling base metal are met.

Post-welding heat treatment – heat treatment necessary to ensure welding quality has been performed.

Inspection and testing before, during and after welding – quality control plan implemented.

Non-conformance and corrective action – non-conforming products are not used as intended, corrective action is taken.

Calibration and validation of measuring instruments, control and measuring devices and test equipment have been performed.

Marking (identification) during processing – done. Traceability is ensured.

Records relating to quality are maintained.

The processes in the above list adjust quality assurance at the appropriate stages of the welding production product life cycle to welding-specific activities.

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